

A DATA FUSION METHOD FOR IMPROVED MOTION ESTIMATION

A.M.Peacock, D.Renshaw, J.Hannah, P.Grant

Department of Electrical Engineering, The University of Edinburgh,
The King's Buildings, Mayfield Road, Edinburgh EH9 3JL, Scotland, UK.

e-mail: amp@ee.ed.ac.uk, dar@ee.ed.ac.uk, john@ee.ed.ac.uk, pgm@ee.ed.ac.uk

ABSTRACT

Previous work has shown that information from different artificial vision approaches to the same problem can be combined using Data Fusion methods to produce more robust results. Different techniques may also have different computational requirements, and there is often a trade off between algorithm complexity and accuracy. This paper reports the use of state and error predictors combined with data fusion methods to create vision systems with improved performance. Results for both synthetic and real examples are reported. These results show that substantial improvements can be made using this temporal-data fusion approach.

1 INTRODUCTION

The relative performance of different image processing techniques varies depending on the image or image sequence being processed. Previous work has shown that data fusion methods can be used to combine the results of different image processing techniques applied to the same frame[1, 2]. In image processing there is often a trade off between accuracy and efficiency. This is a particularly important issue when processing image sequences [3].

It is desirable to combine the accuracy of slower techniques with the speed of less accurate ones. Given that all reasonable image processing techniques take some time to run, the estimates they present must always relate to some earlier time point. Furthermore, different techniques will have different computational requirements, and so if run concurrently will give estimates for different time points.

In the method proposed by this paper, illustrated in Figure(1), an image sequence is processed by a selection of individual techniques. A predictor is associated with each individual technique to predict the state at the current time point. The state may be any result, such as a texture segmentation or optical flow. Data fusion techniques are then be used to combine the estimates for that time point.

Figure 1: The proposed time dependent data fusion system.

2 DATA FUSION

In Data Fusion, information from multiple, often distributed sensors is combined. Classical Bayesian detection theory was first extended to the distributed sensor case by Tenney and Sandell [4]. In the *Centralised* model, a single global decision is made based on the observations of all the sensors. In the *Decentralised* model, there is insufficient bandwidth to transmit the individual observations and so each sensor makes an individual decision which is transmitted to a fusion centre. Decisions are assumed to consume less bandwidth than the original observations.

The data fusion model described in this paper is a mixture of the decentralised and centralised fusion models. Here, the sensors are the output of different algorithms. Although each sensor makes individual decisions which are combined at a fusion centre, the transmitted decisions may actually contain more information than the original data. The data fusion approach used at the fusion centre in this model is described below.

The data fusion problem may be seen as an M hypothesis detection problem, with hypotheses $h_m \in H$, where N individual detector decisions x_n form the observation $\mathbf{x} = \{x_0, \dots, x_{N-1}\} \in \mathbf{X}$ [5]. The task can then be approached using classical decision theory [6].

The observation space $\mathbf{X}$ is split into disjoint regions X_i , so that given an observation $\mathbf{x}$, if $\mathbf{x} \in X_i$ then hypothesis h_i is chosen. The expected cost or *risk* R for the decision system can be shown to be [6]:

$$R = \sum_{h_j \in H} P_j \lambda_{jj} + \sum_{h_i \in H} \int_{X_i} \sum_{h_j \in H - h_i} P_j (\lambda_{ij} - \lambda_{jj}) p(\mathbf{x}|h_j) d\mathbf{x} \quad (1)$$

where λ_{ij} is the cost associated with choosing hypothesis h_i when h_j is true, and $P_j = P(h_j)$ is the *a priori* probability of hypothesis h_j . $p(\mathbf{x}|h_j)$ is the probability distribution of observing $\mathbf{x}$ given that h_j actually occurred. The first sum is the fixed cost of the decision system and the second term is the cost dependent on the choice of decision region boundaries. The minimum of this risk function is when the decision regions X_i are assigned to minimise the integrands in Equation(1). The minimisation can be achieved by comparing pairs of integrands for different $h_i \in H$. The comparisons may be rearranged to give:

$$P_l (\lambda_{kl} - \lambda_{ll}) p(\mathbf{x}|h_l) \underset{\text{not } l}{\overset{\text{not } k}{\geq}} P_k (\lambda_{lk} - \lambda_{kk}) p(\mathbf{x}|h_k) + \sum_{h_j \in H - \{h_k, h_l\}} P_j (\lambda_{lj} - \lambda_{kj}) p(\mathbf{x}|h_j) \quad (2)$$

Since the observation $\mathbf{x}$ is comprised of the decisions $x_0, \dots, x_{N-1}$ with individual distributions $p(x_i|h)$, $p(\mathbf{x}|h)$ can be determined if the $p(x_i|h)$ distributions and their inter-dependencies are known.

In many image processing techniques, the uncertainty is not best described by probability distributions. The data fusion methods described here therefore represent uncertainty using fuzzy methods [1].

3 STATE PREDICTION

The accuracy of image processing techniques tends to be inversely proportional to technique complexity. Since all reasonable image processing techniques take time $t > 0$ to run, the state estimate of an observer will always relate to some earlier time. It is assumed that techniques can make predictions about future states of the observed process and can give a measure of confidence in these predictions. This is a reasonable assumption and given some reasonable continuity and rate of change assumptions a Kalman filter[8] could be used to provide these values.

A fusion centre periodically requests from all techniques the state and confidence estimates for a given time point. These predicted state estimates are then combined using the data fusion methods described above. The longer the time between the last observation made by a technique and the predicted state estimate, the larger the expected error variance, and so the less the state estimate will be valued in determining the fused

Figure 2: Individual and fused state estimates for simulated data.

state estimate. In this way, information from all techniques is used when estimating the state at any time point.

4 RESULTS - SIMULATION DATA

Consider a process where an object is moving in a straight line at some constant velocity away from a point. The distance x at time t of the object from its initial position is described by the following equations:

$$x_t = x_{t-1} + T x'_{t-1} \quad (3)$$

$$x'_t = x'_{t-1} + U_{t-1} \quad (4)$$

where x' is the velocity of the object with $U \sim N(0, u)$ a random variable simulating unknown influences on the process. Two observers, A and B , are acting. A makes more frequent but less accurate observations than B . Observations y are simulated by random variables $y_t = x_t + Q_t$, with $Q \sim N(0, q)$.

Each observer uses a Kalman filter to maintain an estimate $\hat{x}$ of the current state. At each time step, a fusion centre takes an estimate of the current state and an error estimate from both observers. The state and error estimates are provided by the predictor equations of the Kalman Filter [8]. Equal prior probabilities and the Minimum Probability of Error cost function[6] are assumed and so (1) simplifies to:

$$p(\mathbf{x}|h_l) \underset{\text{not } l}{\overset{\text{not } k}{\geq}} p(\mathbf{x}|h_j) \quad (5)$$

The individual results are also assumed to be independent so that $p((\hat{x}_A, \hat{x}_B)|h_j) = p(\hat{x}_A|h_j) \cdot p(\hat{x}_B|h_j)$. The individual pdf's are assumed to be Gaussian distributions with mean and variance given by the state and error variance estimates from the Kalman predictor equations.

The process was run for 200 time steps with $u = 1$, $q_A = 25$, $q_B = 1$. A makes observations at every time

step, B makes observations every 5 time steps. Figure(2) shows the predicted state estimates for each Process and the fused estimate for time steps 100 to 150. Over 1000 time steps, the mean error of the state estimates of A and B were 4.46 and 5.05 respectively (3 s.f.). The mean error of the fused estimate was 3.91, showing a marked improvement using this temporal fusion method.

5 RESULTS - REAL DATA

This method has also been applied to improve the results of previously reported [1, 2] motion estimation techniques. Two Block Matching (BM) based[7] motion estimation techniques and a texture segmentation technique are used.

The first motion estimation technique (A) uses 6×6 reference blocks while the second (B) uses 8×8 blocks. As a result, B makes less frequent observations than A . However, the results for B more accurately portray motion in the scene. In this example, A was assumed to make observations every frame, while B observed only every 5th frame.

A texture segmentation technique C based on the work of Eden and Unser [9] was used to identify road-like texture in the image. Since the road is known to be stationary, this information can be used in the fusion centre to improve the motion estimation results. C was assumed to make observations every frame.

The data fusion approach adopted is an extended version of earlier work described in [2]. Motion vectors are represented by polar coordinates. The maximum velocity considered is v pels per frame. The crisp $2\pi \times v$ possible motion vectors are quantised into $T \times R$ hypotheses, with an additional "no motion" hypothesis, giving $TR + 1 = M$ hypotheses in all.

For simplicity, the motion predictors treat each pel as an individual moving object and determine the next position of the pel based on its current motion estimate. The motion at the predicted position is set to be the same as the current motion. Confidence in the hypothesis reduces linearly with the prediction time.

Again it is assumed that the individual techniques are independent, that all motions are equally likely, and the Minimum Probability of Error cost function[6] was used. Since appropriate distributions are hard to find, the M hypotheses are represented by triangular fuzzy sets and combined using the fuzzy AND function[10].

5.1 Results

Figure(3) shows one frame result from applying this technique to the Hamburg Taxi sequence. A section of each frame was segmented by hand into moving and stationary regions. The section was chosen to have a similar number of pels with and without motion. The number of pels falsely found to be moving/stationary could then be determined to give a rough estimate of the accuracy of the results. In the section of the Hamburg

Figure 3: Combining results of Motion Estimation techniques. Example image (a), Misclassified pels in 6×6 BM (b), 8×8 BM (c), Fused Result (d).

Taxi Sequence shown in Figure(3), the average errors of A and B were 15% and 13% misclassified pels respectively. The averaged fused error was 8% misclassified.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This paper considers the problem of data fusion where observations of a process are processed by different techniques at different speeds and with different accuracies. It is desirable to combine the speed of the less accurate techniques with the accuracy of the slower ones, while taking account of the fact that estimates from the individual techniques may relate to different and previous time points. A method has been presented which uses filters to predict the state estimates for the individual techniques at the current time point, then combines the state estimates using data fusion methods.

Results from simulated and real data illustrate that valuable improvements may be made using this data fusion approach. Future work will extend the range of image processing techniques applied to this data fusion method.

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